

THE INFLUENCE OF SUPRAMOLECULAR MICROSTRUCTURES ON THE LOAD TRANSFER EFFICIENCY FOR SINGLE CARBON NANOTUBE FIBER EMBEDDED POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

Interfacial adhesion between polymer matrices and fillers play a critical role in the mechanical performance of composites. The strong interfacial adhesion will result in efficient load transfer from matrices to fillers, and thereby the mechanical enhancements are expected. During the past decades, considerable attention has been paid to build chemical or physical bonding between polymer matrices and fillers. While the interfacial morphology influence on the load transfer efficiency have not been considered yet in detail. As a novel fiber material, carbon nanotube (CNT) fibers have attracted great interests owing to their multiple functionalities, e.g., electrical, mechanical, and thermal properties. Recent work has demonstrated that the highest tensile strength of CNT fiber could reach 9 GPa, which surpassed all of the commercial fiber materials.[1] This encouraging breakthrough greatly enlightens the use of CNTs fibers as structural reinforcements for polymer matrices.

Based on our recent work, herein, we fabricate the single CNTs fiber embedded isotactic polypropylene (iPP) model composite. The formed polymer transcrystallinity layer (TCL) indicated that CNTs could act as heterogeneous nucleate agents. [2-4] Due to its anisotropic feature, TCL has significant influence on the performances of fiber-matrix interfaces, and hence affects greatly the mechanical properties of resulting composites. By controlling the melting crystallization temperature as well as the cooling rate, three different types of interfacial supramolecular microstructures of PP transcrystals

were formed, namely αI , αII , and αIII . Further microstructure characterizations based on SEM also support our observation. The influence of varied interfacial morphology on the load transfer efficiency was evaluated using micro-Raman technology. Our results have found out that the αII transcrystal interphase can transfer more loads as compared to αI and αIII transcrystal interphases. In addition, the interfacial strength derived from single fiber pull-out tests also show the same behaviors as that obtained from the micro-Raman tests. The effect of microstructures of TCL on the load transfer efficiency will be beneficial to the design of high performance fiber based thermoplastic composites.

2. Experimental

CNTs fibers were prepared according to our previous work, whereby a certain twisting angle was inserted during the twisting process. Typically, the diameter of CNTs fibers ranged from 35 to 45 μm . The semicrystalline matrix polymer used was commercial grade isotactic polypropylene (S1003) with a melt flow index of 3.2 g/10 min. Thin iPP matrix films, $\sim 40 \mu m$ and $\sim 90 \mu m$ in thickness, were prepared by hot-pressing the iPP granules at 190 $^{\circ}C$ with 25 MPa pressure for 10 min.

To study the transcrystallization kinetics, single fiber model composites were prepared as follows: one piece of iPP film ($\sim 40 \mu m$) was placed on a glass slide. Afterwards, a CNTs fiber was placed onto the iPP film. Using hot stage (Linkam TMS94), the temperature was raised up to 200 $^{\circ}C$ over 5 min to erase the previous thermal history of the polymer matrices and then cooled at a rate of 30 $^{\circ}C/min$ to the desired isothermal crystallization temperature

(120~145 °C). A Leica optical microscope (DM4000M) equipped with cross polarizer permitted viewing of the inner cell of the hot stage and crystallization process. The radius of the TCL was measured at certain time intervals until the obscuring of the TCL by the abundant presence of spherulites in the matrix.

In situ Raman compressive tests were used to probe the strain transfer between the iPP matrix and CNTs fiber. The compressive stress applied onto the fibers came from the shrinkage of the surrounding iPP matrix with the temperature decreasing from 60 to -60°C. Raman spectra were collected using the 180° backscattering geometry with the 633 nm line of a HeNe laser. The polarized laser beam was focused on the embedded fiber through a × 50 objective lens with a 2 μm diameter laser spot. The Raman peak position was determined by a mixture of Lorentzian and Gaussian fit to the raw data. In order to elucidate the strain transfer efficiency of various TCL with different birefringence, single fiber composites were prepared by covering a CNTs fiber on a glass slide with one piece of iPP film (~90 μm), which were then melt and crystallized under three different conditions listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Crystallization conditions and birefringence of iPP specimens which were first kept at 200°C for 5 min in order to melt the crystal residues

Birefringence	Crystallization conditions
Positive (α_I)	Crystallized at 132°C for 1 h, then heated to 169°C and cooled to 30°C at 10°C/min
Mixed (α_{III})	Crystallized at 132°C for 1 h
Negative (α_{II})	Crystallized at 140°C for 4 h

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1a shows the SEM images of CNTs fiber, clearly, the fiber surface has some rough microstructures such as grooves or ravines. As CNT fiber was introduced into iPP matrix, the oriented crystalline morphology surrounding the fibers are observed shown in Figure 1b, which is identified as TCL. Away from the CNTs fiber, the iPP spherulites are also observed. The crystalline density of TCL around CNTs fiber looks higher and the lamellae orient much more regularly.

Fig.1. SEM image of the twisted CNTs fiber (a) with the diameter ranged from 35 to 45 μm (b); Optical micrographs of TCL of CNT-iPP model composite.

To investigate the influence of microstructure of TCL on the strain transfer efficiency, three types of TCL of single fiber-iPP model composites with positive, negative or mixed birefringence were prepared as described in Table 1. With the help of a primary red filter (λ -plate), the optical characteristics of the three types of TCL microstructure were easily identified (Figure 2). For the positive birefringent morphology (α_I), one-three quadrant phase is blue and two-four quadrant phase is yellow; by contraries, one-three quadrant phase is yellow and two-four quadrant phase is blue for the negative birefringent morphology (α_{II}); additionally, the mixed birefringent morphologic feature (α_{III}) is yellow and blue alternately. [5]

Raman spectroscopy has been demonstrated to be a useful technique to detect the interfacial behavior in carbon fiber or carbon nanotubes reinforced composites. [6] Since Raman frequency is sensitive to the variations of inter-atomic distance, when carbon fibers or CNTs in composites are stretched or compressed by the load from matrix, there is a linear relationship between the shifts of Raman frequencies and local applied strains. For example, Gamstedt et al. had quantitatively assessed the improved interfacial efficiency of carbon fiber composites with available interfacial modification. [7] Herein, Raman spectroscopy was employed to

analyze the interfacial strain transfer between the iPP matrix and CNTs fiber. Through investigating the variations of Raman G'-band of CNTs fiber under compression mode, we could estimate the compression strain of fibers and further inferred the effect of varied microstructure of TCL on the strain transfer efficiency.

Fig.2. iPP specimens with various birefringence of TCL crystallized at different conditions shown in Table 1: (a) α I ; (b) α II ; (c) α III.

Figure 3a shows the G'-band Raman shifts versus temperature for single CNTs fiber embedded in iPP matrix with three different microstructures of TCL. Significant upward shifts of Raman G'-band are expected with the temperature decreasing from 60 to -60°C, and arise from the shortening of C=C bond length due to the applied compressive stresses from matrix shrinkage. For the CNTs fiber/iPP composites show in Figure 3a, the shift trend of Raman G' band shifts are obviously varied according to the microstructure of TCL layer. The shifts for specimens with negative birefringence TCL are the largest, equal to $\sim 20\text{cm}^{-1}$ at -60°C while that values for mixed birefringence and positive birefringence specimens are relatively smaller,

$\sim 13\text{cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 10\text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively. As stated above, the Raman frequency shifts of CNTs fiber under compression are associated with the variation of C=C bond distance. Thus, the compressive strain of CNTs fiber deformed, termed as $\varepsilon_{\text{fiber}}$, could be deduced from the shifts of Raman frequency. Cronin et al has reported that the shift rate of G'-band for the tensile individual SWNT in elastic region reaches to $37.6\text{cm}^{-1}/1\%$ strain.[8] In general, the fiber material with full crystallinity (such as polydiacetylene fibers, CNTs, HMCF et.al) is expected to have identical shift rates for Raman band under both tension and compression as it deforms elastically. Consequently, the strain of CNTs fiber ($\varepsilon_{\text{fiber}}$) deformed in single fiber-composite systems could be obtained by Eq. 1:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{fiber}} = \frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega/1\%} = \frac{(\omega_c - \omega_0)}{\omega/1\%} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

where ω_0 and ω_c present G'-band frequencies at 60 °C and at a certain low temperature respectively. In addition, the shrinkage strain of the surrounding matrix are calculated by Eq. 2:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{matrix}} = \Delta\alpha\Delta T \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

in which $\Delta\alpha = \alpha_{\text{matrix}} - \alpha_{\text{fiber}}$, α_{matrix} and α_{fiber} are the thermal expansion coefficients of matrix and fiber respectively; ΔT is the temperature gradient for which 60°C is the reference temperature. To illuminate the interface behavior well, we define strain transfer factor (STF) of interface as the ratio of the strain of the embedded fiber to that of the surrounding matrix.

$$STF = \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{fiber}}}{\varepsilon_{\text{matrix}}} \times 100\% \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

The STF can give us a direct evaluation of how much strain comes from the matrix to the embedded fiber. Figure 3b show the calculated STF versus temperature for CNTs fibers/iPP model composites with different microstructure of TCL. Apparently, for the CNTs fibers/iPP composites, STF is closely related to the microstructures of the TCL with an order: α I > α II > α III. For example, at 0°C the STF value for model composite with negative birefringence is ~ 0.45 , while that values for mixed birefringence and positive birefringence are much smaller, ~ 0.30 and ~ 0.20 respectively. This variation reflects that the microstructures of TCL evidently influence the strain transfer and negative

birefringence microstructure is relatively most favorable to the load transfer efficiency.

Figure 3 (a) Raman shifts of G' band for CNTs fiber/iPP model composites as a function of temperature. Based on the Raman shifts, the STF versus temperature for CNTs fibers/iPP; (b) model composites with different morphologic TCL were deduced

4. Conclusion

In summary, CNTs fibers could act as favorable nucleating agents for iPP transcrystallization. With the help of micro-Raman spectroscopy, the effect of microstructures of various TCL on the strain transfer efficiency has been fully investigated. Negative birefringence of TCL (α_{II}) is most favorable to the load transfer, while positive birefringence of TCL (α_{I}) is relatively adverse. Based on the micrographs of three types of TCL, it is concluded that the lamellae orientations significantly influence the interface properties.

References

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